

THE WEAR RATE OF BEARING ELEMENTS IN THE PRESENCE OF ABRASIVE PARTICLES IN THE UNIT OIL

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Abstract. This article presents the results of theoretical studies on the wear rate of rolling bearing components in the presence of abrasive particles in the unit's oil. It is noted that increasing the strength, size, and concentration of abrasive particles increases the wear rate of rolling bearing components, while increasing the mechanical properties of the bearing component material decreases the wear rate.

Keywords: Rolling bearings, inner (outer) ring, ball, abrasive wear, spherical abrasive particle, wedge-shaped gap, concentration, elastic deformation, material hardness, friction path, penetration depth.

INTRODUCTION

When operating machines in dusty conditions, significant amounts of abrasive particles accumulate in the oil. Research shows that 79.4% of rolling bearings fail due to abrasive wear under these conditions.

Abrasive wear results in rapid wear of all bearing components, altering their geometric shape and dimensions. This, in turn, leads to increased radial and axial clearances in the bearing and accelerated bearing failure [1 - 8]. Abrasive wear is most often observed in bearings of industrial machines, agricultural machinery, and other machine components that are inadequately protected from soil and dust.

Abrasive wear of rolling bearing components occurs as follows. A spherical abrasive particle enters the wedge-shaped gap of the friction surfaces and begins to move toward the contact surface under the action of friction. The compressive normal load acting on the abrasive particle increases, and depending on the increase in this load, the depth of its penetration into the friction surface increases. Once the abrasive particle penetrates the friction surface to a certain depth, further increases in the normal load lead to fragmentation of the abrasive particle. I.V. Kragelsky noted that repeated fragmentation of an abrasive particle in a wedge-shaped gap can occur up to seven times [1, 4, 5, 7].

Wear of rolling bearing components occurs as follows. Abrasive particles, modeled as a sphere,

penetrate the wedge-shaped gap between the surfaces. Under the influence of the frictional force generated between the bearing components, they begin to slide relative to the mating friction surfaces of the bearing toward the contact zone of the rubbing surfaces. This increases the normal load acting on the abrasive particle, leading to an increase in its penetration depth and an increase in the deformation volume of the rolling surfaces.

In the elastic deformation zone, the number of cycles leading to the formation of wear debris is several times greater than during plastic deformation of the friction surfaces. Therefore, in the calculations of bearing components, we will not consider wear of bearing components resulting from elastic deformation. The number of deformation cycles leading to the destruction of the friction surface depends on the coefficient of relative elongation, the probability of fixation of abrasive particles and the hardness of the material.

RESEARCH METHODS

In practical rolling bearing manufacturing, its components are typically made from the same material and undergo the same heat treatment, resulting in identical hardness. Therefore, the probability of abrasive particles becoming embedded (α^1) in the friction surfaces of the inner and outer bearing rings will be the same,

$$\alpha^1 = H_{in} / (H_{in} + H_b) = H_{ou} / (H_{ou} + H_b),$$

where, H_{in} , H_{ou} , H_b – are the hardness of the material of the inner, outer rings and the ball, respectively.

Then,

$$H = H_{in} = H_{ou} = H_b.$$

According to the fixation condition, the friction path of abrasive particles on the friction surfaces of the inner (outer) ring and ball,

$$s_{in,ou} = \pi \cdot d_b \cdot (i_{1,2} \pm 1) \cdot (1 - \cos \beta_i) \cdot H / (H + H_b). \quad (1)$$

where, $s_{in,ou(1,2)}$ – is the sliding path between the inner (outer) ring and the ball; $i_{1,2}$ – is the ratio of the diameter of the inner (outer) ring along their groove to the diameter of the ball,

$$i_{1,2} = \frac{d_{in,ou}}{d_b}.$$

The friction path of the ball relative to the inner (outer) ring,

$$s_{bi}^{m,ou} = s_{i(1,2)} \cdot \beta^1 - \pi \cdot d_b \cdot (i_{1,2} \pm 1) \cdot (1 - \cos \beta_i) \cdot H_b / (H + H_b). \quad (2)$$

where, β^1 – is the probability of abrasive particles becoming fixed on the ball's surface. According to the above condition $\alpha^1 = \beta^1$.

We calculate the penetration depth of abrasive particles involved in the wear process into the surface of the inner and outer rings and the ball:

$$h = d_{av} \cdot H / (H + H_b). \quad (3)$$

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по [5]:

into the surface of the inner and outer rings,

$$h = h_{in} = h_{ou} = d_{av} \cdot \sigma_a / 4 \cdot H, \quad (4)$$

where, σ_a - compressive strength of an abrasive particle.

into the surface of the ball,

$$h_b = d_{av} \cdot \sigma_a / H_b. \quad (5)$$

Using expressions (1) and (5), we determine the friction path of an abrasive particle before crushing:

along the surface of the inner (outer) ring, relative to the ball,

$$S_{in,ou(m)} = \frac{\pi \cdot d_{m,ou} \cdot (i_{1,2} \pm 1) \cdot (1 - \cos \beta_i) \cdot \sigma_a}{4 \cdot (H + H_b)}, \quad (6)$$

along the surface of the ball, relative to the inner (outer) ring,

$$S_{bi(m)}^{m,ou} = \frac{\pi \cdot d_b \cdot (i_{1,2} \pm 1) \cdot (1 - \cos \beta_i) \cdot \sigma_a}{4 \cdot (H + H_b)}. \quad (7)$$

We determine the largest area of the base of the deformed friction surface in a perpendicular section along the direction of movement of the abrasive particle:

for the inner and outer rings,

$$F = d_{av}^2 \cdot G \cdot \sigma_a / (60 \cdot H), \quad (8)$$

where, G - is a coefficient taking into account the ratio of the hardness of the friction surface and the strength of the abrasive particle:

$$G = 3 \cdot (H \cdot \sigma_a - \sigma_a^2)^{1/2} / H + 4 \cdot (\sigma_a / H)^{1/2},$$

for the ball,

$$F_b = d_{av}^2 \cdot G \cdot \sigma_a / (60 \cdot H_b). \quad (9)$$

The number of abrasive particles located, at a length equal to the friction path of the abrasive particle before its crushing, on the surface of the inner (outer) ring:

$$n_{m,ou(m)} = \frac{0,435 \cdot \pi \cdot d_b \cdot (i_{1,2} \pm 1) \cdot (1 - \cos \beta_i^m) \cdot \sigma_a \cdot \varepsilon_k^{1/2}}{d_{av} \cdot (H + H_b)}. \quad (10)$$

The total number of abrasive particles in the contact zone before they are crushed,

$$n^{in,ou} = \frac{0,26 \cdot d_b^2 \cdot (i_{1,2} \pm 1) \cdot (1 - \cos \beta_i) \cdot \sigma_a \cdot \varepsilon_k \cdot \beta_i}{d_{av}^2 \cdot (H + H_b)}. \quad (11)$$

The volume of deformation of friction surfaces by abrasive particles located between the ball and the inner (outer) ring,

$$V_{in,ou} = \frac{34 \cdot 10^{-4} \cdot \sigma_a^3 \cdot G \cdot d_b^3 \cdot (i_{1,2} \pm 1)^2 \cdot (1 - \cos \beta_i)^2 \cdot \varepsilon_k \cdot \beta_i}{H \cdot (H + H_b)^2}, \quad (12)$$

volume of deformation of the ball,

$$v_{b(1,2)} = \frac{34 \cdot 10^{-4} \cdot \sigma_a^3 \cdot G \cdot d_b^3 \cdot (i_{1,2} \pm 1)^2 \cdot (1 - \cos \beta_i)^2 \cdot \varepsilon_k \cdot \beta_i}{H \cdot (H + H_b)^2} \quad (13)$$

The total volume of deformation of the ball by abrasive particles,

$$v_b = \frac{34 \cdot 10^{-4} \cdot \sigma_a^3 \cdot G \cdot d_b^3 \cdot \varepsilon_k \cdot ((i_{1,2} + 1)^2 \cdot (1 - \cos \beta_i)^2 + (i_2 + 1)^2 \cdot (1 - \cos \beta_i)^2) \cdot \beta_i}{H_b \cdot (H + H_b)^2} \quad (14)$$

The area of deformation of the friction surface before the onset of crushing of abrasive particles:

grooves of the inner (outer) ring,

$$F_{din,ou} = \frac{\beta_i \cdot d_b^2 \cdot (i_{1,2} \pm 1) \cdot (1 - \cos \beta_i) \cdot \sigma_a}{72 \cdot (H + H_b)} \quad (15)$$

surface of the ball,

$$F_{db(1,2)} = \frac{d_b^2 \cdot \sigma_a \cdot (i_{1,2} \pm 1) \cdot (1 - \cos \beta_i) \cdot \beta_i}{72 \cdot (H + H_b)} \quad (16)$$

The probability of repeated deformation by abrasive particles of the same surface of the inner (outer) ring:

the raceways of the inner (outer) ring,

$$\eta_{in,ou} = 4,17 \cdot d_{av} / (i_{1,2} \cdot \varepsilon_k^{1/2} \cdot \beta_i \cdot d_b) \quad (17)$$

The number of loading cycles leading to the destruction of the re-formed volume of friction surface metal:

inner (outer) ring and ball,

$$n_{pin,ou,b} = \psi_{in,ou,b}^t \quad (18)$$

where $\psi_{in,ou,b}$ – is the coefficient of relative elongation of the material of the inner, outer rings and ball; t – is the coefficient of frictional fatigue of the material of the part, for steel $t=1.3$.

The coefficient taking into account the misalignment of the inner ring relative to the outer ring θ_{ou} of the bearing,

$$\theta_m = \left[1 + [(\exp(\beta_i \cdot 0,9995)^{3,5})^6 - 1] \right] \quad (19)$$

Taking into account the values of v_{ou} from (12); $F_{din,ou}$ from (15); $n_{pin,ou,b}$ from (18) and θ_{ou} from (19), after some simplification, we obtain an expression for calculating the wear rate of the elements (inner, outer rings and ball) of a rolling bearing:

$$y_{in,ou,b} = \frac{1,836 \cdot \sigma_a^2 \cdot G \cdot d_{av} \cdot \varepsilon_k^{1/2} \cdot n \cdot n_b \cdot (i_{1,2} \pm 1) \cdot \theta_{ou}}{(n_{p(in,ou)} \cdot H_{in,ou,b} \cdot (H_{in,ou} + H_b) \cdot i_{1,2})} \quad (20)$$

CONCLUSIONS

Thus, the obtained dependence and the results of calculation using expression (20) show that with an increase in strength, size, concentration of abrasive particles and the angle of skew of the rings, the wear rate of the bearing elements (inner, outer rings and ball) increases, and with an increase in the

coefficient of relative elongation and hardness of the material, the wear rate of the elements of the rolling ball bearing decreases.

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